

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes. Part-XXIII[†] : Direct electrochemical synthesis of bismuth(III) alkoxides

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Abstract : Bismuth(III) alkoxides have been synthesized by electrochemical reactions of methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol, *n*-pentanol, *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol, *n*-octanol, *n*-onanol, *n*-decanol at sacrificial bismuth anode and inert platinum cathode using tetrabutylammonium chloride as supporting electrolyte and acetonitrile as solvent. The solid products separated in the anode compartment have been isolated and characterized by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies. Current efficiencies of these reactions are quite high.

Keywords : Bismuth(III) alkoxide, electrochemical reaction, sacrificial electrodes.

Introduction

Bismuth(III) alkoxides are excellent precursors for the deposition of metal oxides, and current interest in using metal oxides, in optoelectronics, high- T_c bismuth-containing superconductors, sol-gel¹, MOCVD²⁻⁴ process and ceramics has led to a resurgence of interest in the chemistry of these compounds. The synthesis of bismuth(III) alkoxides (methoxide, ethoxide and isopropoxide) had been described⁵ for the first time by Mehrotra and Rai in 1966 by the methatic reactions between bismuth trichloride and the corresponding alkali alkoxides in benzene.

But the work was not pursued much further in any laboratory and no systematic attempt has been made to synthesize and characterize homometallic bismuth(III) alkoxides due to the observed difficulties in their preparation. However heterobimetallic alkoxides of bismuth are reported in literature⁶⁻¹⁰. In the present communication we report the direct electrochemical synthesis of bismuth(III) alkoxides. In electrochemical reactions of alcohols at various metal anodes, metal alkoxide¹¹⁻¹³ is formed as a result of replacement of protons of alcohol molecules with anodic metal. Here we report the electrochemical reactions of various alcohols at sacrificial bismuth anode.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical reactions of alcohols at sacrificial bismuth anode and inert platinum cathode yield bismuth

alkoxides. The mechanism of the reaction is as given below :

At inert cathode :

At sacrificial anode :

In order to determine the bismuth contents by oxine method¹⁴ accurately weighed (0.05 g) product was heated to dryness six times with 2.0 mL of fuming nitric acid. The dry mass was dissolved in 1.0 mL of concentrated nitric acid and diluted to 100 mL with distilled water. Carbon and hydrogen contents in the products were determined through microanalysis. The bismuth contents (Table 1) in these compounds correspond to general formula $Bi(OR)_3$.

Melting point of all these products was determined using electrical device with a heating rate of 5 °C per minute. It has been observed that these compounds decompose at a temperature of about 200–250 °C and do not melt. The decomposition of products is indicated from the change in colour of these compounds.

Solubility of all these compounds has been determined in various commonly used organic solvents like chloroform, benzene, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, methanol, carbon tetrachloride, acetone, dimethylsulfoxide and toluene. All these compounds are insoluble in these solvents.

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Table 1. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical and other related data of electrolysis of alcohols at bismuth anode

System	Potential (V)	Electricity passed (Coulombs)	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :			Current efficiencies (gram equivalent/ Faraday)
					Found (Calcd.)			
					Bi	C	H	
Methanol	50	864	Bi(OCH ₃) ₃	Brown	67.0 (69.2)	10.2 (11.9)	1.8 (2.9)	0.84
Ethanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃	Light brown	58.5 (60.7)	19.8 (20.9)	4.1 (4.4)	0.78
<i>n</i> -Propanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₃ H ₇) ₃	Brown	54.0 (54.1)	27.3 (27.9)	5.0 (5.4)	0.79
<i>n</i> -Butanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₄ H ₉) ₃	Creamy white	48.6 (48.8)	32.8 (33.6)	5.9 (6.3)	0.79
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₅ H ₁₁) ₃	Light brown	43.8 (44.4)	38.0 (38.2)	6.5 (7.0)	0.82
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₆ H ₁₃) ₃	Light brown	39.7 (40.8)	41.7 (42.1)	7.3 (7.6)	0.81
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₇ H ₁₅) ₃	Light brown	37.6 (37.7)	45.2 (45.4)	7.9 (8.1)	0.83
<i>n</i> -Octanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₈ H ₁₇) ₃	Light brown	35.0 (35.0)	48.0 (48.3)	8.5 (8.6)	0.79
<i>n</i> -Nonanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₉ H ₁₉) ₃	Brown	32.5 (32.7)	50.4 (50.7)	8.5 (8.9)	0.83
<i>n</i> -Decanol	50	864	Bi(OC ₁₀ H ₂₁) ₃	Brown	29.0 (30.7)	52.7 (52.9)	9.0 (9.3)	0.83

Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI) in the region of 4000–450 cm⁻¹ using potassium bromide pellets. It has been observed that all of these compounds do not show any absorption band in the region of 3600–3400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to hydroxyl group of alcohols, which show that the product is completely free from alcohol and solvated alkoxides. However, characteristic bands appear in the region of 1150–1000 cm⁻¹ and 550–540 cm⁻¹.

Survey of literature reveals¹⁵ that the metal-oxygen stretching frequencies generally appear in the range of 700–500 cm⁻¹. Thus the absorption bands present in the region of 550–540 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Bi-O})$ stretching vibrations¹⁶. Presence of these bands and absence of band due to hydroxyl group in the electrochemical products indicate that the hydrogen of the alcohols have been replaced by the anodic bismuth.

Review of literature reveals^{11,17} that the absorption bands due to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ M stretching vibrations appear in the region of 1150–1000 cm⁻¹ in various metal alkoxides. Transition metal alkoxides generally exist as polymers by

forming bridged structure through alkoxy groups.

It has been reported^{17,18} that infrared data of metal alkoxides show the existence of two types of $\nu(\text{C-O})$ M absorption bands. The terminal alkoxide groups show absorption bands in the region of 1190–1040 cm⁻¹ and bridged alkoxide groups show absorption bands¹⁵ in the region of 1040–940 cm⁻¹. Infrared spectra of the present electrochemical products show the appearance of two/three absorption bands in the region of 1150–1000 cm⁻¹. Infrared spectra of these compounds also reveal that bands appeared due to bridged alkoxide groups in case of compounds of lower alcohols are of medium intensity whereas bands due to terminal alkoxide groups are weak. But in case of compounds of higher alcohols, the bands due to bridged alkoxide groups are weak.

Direct current was obtained by using Toshniwal electrophoresis power supply.

Procedure :

Solution of tetrabutylammonium chloride (0.005 M) and 1.0 ml alcohol in 250.0 ml of acetonitrile was taken in the electrochemical cell. Necessary connections were

then made with the power supply and potential across the electrodes was so adjusted that a current of about 20 mA passed through the cell. The cell is represented as :

where : Bi₍₊₎ is bismuth anode and Pt₍₋₎ is platinum cathode.

Electrolysis was carried out for about twelve hours with continuous stirring. As the electrolysis proceeded, white/brown coloured solid product started separating in the anode compartment. These products were filtered, washed repeatedly with hot acetonitrile and dry ether in an all glass filtration unit and dried in vacuum.

Current efficiencies were determined from the ratio of actual and theoretical amounts of bismuth dissolved when a current of 20.0 mA was passed for 2 h through the cell in the given system. The current efficiencies of these reactions are quite high and have been reported in Table 1.

The present studies thus provide a new route for the synthesis of bismuth(III) alkoxides. It is a single pot and direct synthetic method associated with high current efficiencies.

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